

N-Heterocyclic Carbene-Stabilized Ruthenium Nanoparticles: a Case Study for Ligands Location and their Influence on Reactivity**

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((Dedication---optional))

Despite the huge number of papers dealing with the preparation and use of metal nanoparticles (NPs), in particular for catalysis, very few of them are dedicated to the understanding of the surface chemistry and the influence of organic ligands both on the chemistry and on the physics of the nanoparticles.^[1] The most successful recent class of ligands in organometallic chemistry is no doubt the N-Heterocyclic Carbene (NHC) one.^[2] There are however to the best of our knowledge only three papers dealing with the use of NHC ligands for stabilizing or modifying nanoparticles.^[3-5] Among them, only the one of Tilley et al. reports the use of NHC to synthesize gold NPs.^[3] The others describe the addition of a chiral NHC modifier to Pd nanoparticles supported on iron oxide,^[4] and the substitution of ligands by NHC but leading to unstable particles.^[5] In addition, two papers propose the intermediacy of NHC in the stabilization of nanoparticles in ionic liquids.^[6] None of these papers deals with the characterization of the coordination mode of the NHC ligands onto the nanoparticles surface. Classical carbenes have been used successfully for the stabilization of ruthenium nanoparticles.^[7] The NHC ligands have however many advantages such as their strong electron donating properties, their strong binding to transition metals, their absence of oxidation in contrast to e.g. phosphines and the fact that they contain only C, H and N and no other heteroatom which makes them ideal candidates for stabilizing catalysts.^[8] It is therefore astonishing not to find more examples on the use of these ligands for the stabilization of nanoparticles and hence important to

determine whether these ligands are suitable or not in this field.

We have recently developed the use of various NMR methods in order to understand the mode of coordination and the dynamics of ligands and adsorbates on the surface of nanoparticles.^[9] This is in our opinion the key to control the growth and the surface state of nanoparticles, and further to reach new selective catalysts. Thus, many in situ and operando techniques have been recently developed^[10] but alternative simple methods, similar to the molecular ones, NMR in particular, could bring additional information on the reaction sites and possibly on reaction intermediates.^[9,11] For example, we have determined on ruthenium nanoparticles sterically stabilized by a polymer, PVP, the location and dynamics of hydrides as well as their reactivity towards olefins leading to a facile splitting of a carbon-carbon bond.^[9b]

Here we report the use of NHC ligands, namely N,N-di(*tert*-butyl)imidazol-2-ylidene (**L**₁)^[10] and 1,3-bis(2,6-diisopropylphenyl)imidazol-2-ylidene (**L**₂)^[11] to stabilize Ru nanoparticles and the control of NHC binding by the control of the substituents on nitrogen. In addition, thanks to the synthesis of the analogous ligands ¹³C labeled on the carbene carbon, we report NMR evidence for NHC binding to nanoparticles, and the use of chemical reactivity (ligand exchange, CO binding, CO oxidation, styrene hydrogenation) to characterize the surface and the location of the ligands.

Ruthenium nanoparticles were synthesized by decomposition of (1,5-cyclooctadiene)(1,3,5-cyclooctatriene)ruthenium (0) [(Ru(COD)(COT))] in pentane at room temperature under 3 bar H₂ and in the presence of variable amounts of the carbene ligands **L**₁ or **L**₂, substituted respectively by *tert*-butyl and 2,6 di-isopropylphenyl groups (see Scheme 1). Different [ligand]/[Ru] molar ratios were tested to find the best reaction conditions to obtain well-controlled RuNPs.

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Scheme 1. N-heterocyclic carbenes and reaction conditions used for the synthesis of ruthenium nanoparticles.

Reaction of [Ru(COD)(COT)] with 0.2 equiv. **L**₁ leads to a black precipitate and an absence of stabilization of the nanoparticles. However, using 0.5 equiv. **L**₁, a brown stable colloidal solution is formed. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis revealed the presence of non agglomerated nanoparticles of 1.7(0.2) nm mean size, displaying a narrow size distribution and adopting the hcp

structure of bulk ruthenium as revealed by Fast Fourier Transform analysis (Colloid 1, Figure 1).

Figure 1. TEM and HREM images with corresponding size histogram of Colloid 1 ($[tBu]/[Ru]=0.5$).

The analogous reaction carried out in the presence of 0.2 or 0.5 molar equiv. of L_2 leads to stable colloidal solutions in both cases (Colloids 2 and 3, respectively). TEM and HRTEM analyses revealed the presence of non agglomerated, spherical, monodisperse and highly crystalline nanoparticles (Figure S2 and S3, SI) with mean sizes slightly decreasing from 1.7(0.2) nm in the case of the $[L_2]/[Ru] = 0.2$ system, to 1.5(0.2) for $[L_2]/[Ru] = 0.5$. Higher ligand concentrations thus lead to smaller particles, as previously observed in other systems.^[11b] Upon further addition of ligands (1 equiv.), even smaller particles were observed (1.2 nm) but associated with molecular species as revealed by 1H NMR.

HREM study of Colloid 3 ($[L_2]/[Ru] = 0.5$) (Figure S4, ESI) shows unambiguously the highly crystalline character of the particles and evidence their hexagonal close packed structure for which Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) shows reflections corresponding to the (0-111), (1-101) and (10-10) atomic planes. The hcp structure of the different colloids is also evidenced by Wide-Angle X-ray Scattering (WAXS) measurements performed on powder samples after evaporation of the solvent. Moreover, the coherence lengths of the different samples are found to be 2.0, 1.7 and 1.7 for Colloids 1, 2 and 3 respectively, in good agreement with the mean sizes of the particles determined by HRTEM and hence with the crystalline nature of the particles.

The nanoparticles in colloids 1-3 are stable and can be handled like molecular complexes. The surface species were studied by spectroscopic techniques as well as by titration for the surface hydrides. The latter method is based on the hydrogenation of olefins in the absence of added dihydrogen and that can hence be only induced by the existing surface hydrides (see ESI).^[14] The resulting values are 1.1, 1.3 and 2.5 H/Ru_s for Coll. 1, 2 and 3 respectively (see Table S2, ESI). They are in agreement with those previously found for PVP- and dppb-stabilized RuNPs.^[9b,11d] The result for colloid 3 is however quite high and may result from transfer dehydrogenation of the alkyl group of L_2 in excess as suggested by NMR studies, in a way similar to that used originally by Crabtree et al. to dehydrogenate alkanes.^[15] This therefore leaves a surface density of hydrides and demonstrates the high reactivity of these RuNPs for hydrogen transfer.

All systems have been characterized by infrared spectroscopy, for which no salient feature has been found but which confirms the presence of carbenes, as well as by solid state and solution NMR spectroscopy after dissolution of the particles into toluene- d_8 . The 1H NMR spectrum of Colloid 1 only shows a broad signal around 1.4 ppm attributed to the *t*Bu groups but no signals in the 6-7 ppm region where the *CH* protons of the imidazole backbone are

expected. The absence of signals for groups immobilized close to nanoparticle surfaces has previously been observed by solution NMR.^[11b,16,17] It is characteristic of the coordination of the ligands at the surface of the particles and results both from the slow tumbling of the particles in solution leading to fast T_2 relaxation and from surface heterogeneity.^[18] Such a phenomenon has also been observed by Tilley and co-workers in the characterization of NHCs stabilized gold nanoparticles.^[3] In the case of Colloid 2, no signals corresponding to the aromatic protons of the phenyl rings, the *CH* imidazole protons and the *CH*-isopropyl proton ($-CH(CH_3)_2$) groups are visible. A very broad signal is only discernable in the 1.0-1.8 ppm region for the methyl groups together with some hydrogenated carbene, as in colloid 1. The analysis of the 1H NMR spectrum of Colloid 3 leads to the same conclusion. These observations demonstrate the rigidity of the coordination of both L_1 and L_2 carbene ligands on the ruthenium surface. In addition, in the case of colloid 2, it suggests a close proximity of the phenyl rings to the surface of the particles and possibly their participation in the stabilization of the nanoparticles through a π or an agostic interaction. We previously observed a similar NMR behavior in the case of RuNPs stabilized with the 4-(3-phenylpropyl)pyridine for which π coordination of the phenyl ring was demonstrated.^[17]

To evaluate the strength of the interaction between the carbene ligands and the surface of the nanoparticles, their substitution was attempted by adding an excess of good σ -donor ligands such as diphenylphosphinobutane or dodecanethiol directly in a toluene- d_8 solution of Colloids 1 and 2. This reaction was followed by 1H NMR. The addition of diphenylphosphinobutane to Colloids 1 and 2 and of dodecanethiol to Colloid 1 only showed the signals for the free added ligands (diphosphine or thiol) and no evidence either for the coordination of such ligands or for free L_1 or L_2 in solution. This result confirms that the carbenes are firmly coordinated to the ruthenium surface, in good agreement with the known strong bonds that NHCs form with metal complexes.^[19]

The coordination of the carbene ligands L_1 and L_2 on the surface was studied by solid-state NMR at magic-angle spinning (MAS-NMR) with and without 1H - ^{13}C cross-polarization (CP) with the aim of determining their location and possible dynamics. The CP MAS spectrum of Colloid 1 shows two broad signals near 120 and 55 ppm attributed respectively to the (*CHN*) and ($-C(CH_3)_3$) groups of L_1 as well as a larger signal near 30 ppm for the methyl of the *t*Bu moieties (see Figure S5, ESI). When using L_1 ^{13}C labelled on the carbene carbon (L_1^*), the spectrum of the corresponding colloid, 1^* , shows a broad peak centred at 190 ppm attributed to the coordinated carbene function. Colloids 2 and 3, only show a broad signal near 25 ppm for the *i*Pr carbons and peaks near 125 ppm and 135-150 ppm for the aromatic carbons. However, when using a labelled ligand (L_2^* , colloid 2^*), the coordination of the carbene carbon was observed at 205 ppm (Figure 2). Lower chemical shifts of the carbenic carbon atom in the ^{13}C NMR are consistent with ligand coordination to transition metals. Interestingly, for colloid 3^* which contains excess L_2^* , besides the signal at 205 ppm, another one appears at 195 ppm which does not correspond to the free ligand (216 ppm).^[20] The presence of these two signals suggests different chemical environments for the carbene ligand L_2^* , that could result from coordination at two different Ru sites (Figure 3).

In order to probe the free sites present on the particles surfaces, ^{13}CO was added to solid samples of colloids 1 - 3 in mild conditions (room temperature, 0.5 or 0.6 atm). In the case of colloid 1, the ^{13}C MAS NMR spectrum shows an intense and very broad signal for bridging carbonyl groups centered at 240 ppm with no apparent

Figure 2. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR spectra of colloid **2*** (^{13}C -labeled [IPr]/[Ru]=0.2 NPs).

Figure 4. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR spectra of colloid **1** after exposure to a ^{13}CO atmosphere (0.6 bar; 20h; at RT).

Figure 3. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR spectra of colloid **3*** (^{13}C -labeled [IPr]/[Ru]=0.5 NPs).

Figure 5. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR spectra of colloid **3** after exposure to a ^{13}CO atmosphere (0.5 bar; 20 h; RT).

spinning side band and a weaker but sharper signal near 200 ppm with spinning side bands corresponding to non diffusing terminal carbonyl groups. Using the CP-MAS technique, the intensity of the terminal CO signal increases (Figure 4). This indicates their location in the vicinity of hydrogen carriers, namely the L_1 carbene ligands. Addition of ^{13}CO was also performed on colloids **2** and **3** (or colloids **2*** and **3***) prepared respectively in the presence of 0.2 or 0.5 equiv. of ligand L_2 (or labelled L_2^*). For colloid **2**, a spectrum similar to that of colloid **1** is observed, namely a broad bridging CO signal centered at 240 ppm and rigid terminal CO groups located near hydrogen carriers and overlapping with the carbene signal in the case of colloid **2*** (Figure S13, SI). However, for colloids **3** or **3***, only static terminal CO signals are observed and no (or very little) bridging CO (Figure S7 and S12, SI). Furthermore, at room temperature, Colloid **1** + CO burns in air, Colloid **2** + CO is degraded in air leading to CO oxidation and colloid **3** + CO reacts very slowly with dioxygen in air. This evidences the ability of ruthenium nanoparticles to oxidize CO in mild conditions and also suggests in the case of colloid **3** the deactivation of the reactive faces after coordination of the carbene ligand. The terminal CO groups on the edges are not oxidized.

A typical test reaction for ruthenium nanoparticles is arene hydrogenation. The reaction was carried out at room temperature in THF in the presence of 3 bar H_2 and for a [substrate]/[catalyst] molar ratio of 315 using colloid **1** or colloid **3** as catalysts. In both cases, the reaction proceeds as expected with initially full hydrogenation of the vinyl bond and then hydrogenation of ethylbenzene into ethylcyclohexane. The rates are similar for both colloids but significantly slower than for a simple Ru/PVP system hence suggesting a reactivity limitation due to ruthenium surface covering by the carbene ligands (see ESI).

This set of reactions demonstrates the high affinity of carbene ligands for ruthenium nanoparticles. The nanoparticles are stable in solution and can be used for catalytic reactions. They do not show any sign of fluxionality or ligand dissociation in THF by ^1H NMR

and the carbene ligands are not displaced in solution by diphosphines or thiols. As expected, the carbenes first coordinate on the most exposed atoms of the particles (apexes, edges). In the case of L_1 , only the exposed ruthenium atoms can be linked to the carbene since the bulky *t*Bu groups prevent L_1 from coordinating to a flat surface (see models in SI). In contrast, L_2 can coordinate first on the exposed atoms and on the edges and faces. The availability of coordination sites has been tested by adding CO gas to solid samples of the different colloids. In the case of colloid **1**, the presence of almost only bridging CO reveals the absence of carbene ligand on the faces whereas the edges are encumbered by the bulky ligand. In the case of colloid **3**, on the contrary, the absence of bridging CO is in agreement with the presence of carbene ligands all over the particle although some free coordination sites for terminal CO could be found in the vicinity of the carbene ligands. In addition, the absence of fluxionality of the coordinated CO groups indicates that their mobility is limited by the presence of the carbene ligands. It is however possible to add sequentially the carbene ligands in the case of L_2 leading to a selective complexation of the edges for a low L_2 concentration and leaving the faces accessible for CO coordination. These studies allow us therefore to reach a good knowledge of the nanoparticle surface coordination chemistry. However, two facts raise questions. First, it is necessary to have an excess of ligand L_1 to stabilize colloid **1**, which is not the case for ligand L_2 in colloid **2**, although once coordinated, L_1 is found only on exposed atoms and is not displaced by diphosphine or thiols. To answer this question we have studied the hydrogenation of the carbene ligands in the presence of catalytic amount of [Ru(COD)(COT)] or of preformed colloids. We found that L_1 is easily hydrogenated at room temperature under 3 bars H_2 , first into the unsaturated substituted 1,3-diazacyclopentene and then into the corresponding 1,3-diazacyclopentane. This reaction transforming the carbene carbon into a hydrogen saturated aliphatic carbon has been observed previously during hydrogenation of a Pd^0 bis-carbene complex, although the role of palladium black formed in this process has not

been clarified.^[21] and could explain the necessity of excess **L**₁ to get stable RuNPs since we checked that the products of hydrogenation do not stabilize nanoparticles. However, no hydrogenation (or a very limited one) is observed with **L**₂. It is not clear why but this can result either from an electronic effects (less basic substituents on nitrogen and stabilization by conjugation in the case of **L**₂) or from a stabilization of the structure by ring-metal interactions. The second point concerns styrene hydrogenation which is achieved at comparable rates for colloids **1** and **3**. This reaction requires the π -coordination of the aromatic rings on the nanoparticle faces which, in the case of colloid **3**, are not accessible to CO in a gas/solid reaction. It is however likely that in solution styrene may displace the possible π -interactions developed by the phenyl rings of **L**₂.

In conclusion, we report in this paper the synthesis of stable ruthenium nanoparticles using carbene ligands. Thanks to NMR studies, to the ¹³C labeling of the carbenes and to the addition of ¹³CO, we evidenced the strong binding of the NHC ligands to the surface and were able to propose for them a location on the particles. Furthermore, we provide evidence for the influence of the substituents of the carbenes on the reactivity of the nanoparticles, mainly due to steric effects. This study therefore describes new organometallic objects covered by different species: hydrides, CO, carbenes which can be located, the dynamics of which can be studied and which behave differently as a function of their location on the particles (Figure 6). It therefore is an attempt at the full molecular characterization of the surface of catalytically active nanoparticles.

Figure 6. Space filling model of a 1.8 nm hcp Ru nanoparticle stabilized by 8 **L**₂ NHC ligands and accommodating 1.5 hydrides per surface Ru..

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((N-Heterocyclic Carbene-Stabilized Ruthenium Nanoparticles: a Case Study for Ligands Location and their Influence on Reactivity))

((The synthesis and characterization of novel ruthenium nanoparticles stabilized by N-Heterocyclic Carbene are described. NMR investigations evidence the coordination of the NHC ligands on the surface of the particles, their localization and the surface reactivity of the resulting nanoparticles. It is an attempt at the full molecular characterization of the surface of catalytically active nanoparticles.))

N-Heterocyclic Carbene-Stabilized Ruthenium Nanoparticles: a Case Study for Ligands Location and their Influence on Reactivity

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S1. General, materials and characterization techniques.

All operations were carried out using standard Schlenk tubes, Fischer-Porter bottle techniques or in a glove-box under argon atmosphere. Solvents were purified just before their use under argon: THF (Sigma-Aldrich) by distillation over sodium/benzophenone, pentane (SDS) from solvent purification system. *t*Bu and *i*Pr carbenes were synthesized from previously published methodologies.^[1,2] [Ru(COD)(COT)] was purchased from Nanomeps Toulouse, Argon, CO (N20) and H₂ (3.5) from Air liquid, ¹³CO (¹³C, 99.14%) from Eurisotop, styrene (>99%) from Acros Organics, paraformaldehyde-¹³C (atom 99% ¹³C) from Sigma-Aldrich; all the reactants were used without any purification.

RuNPs were observed by TEM and HRTEM after deposition of a drop of the crude pentane colloidal solution or a drop of a solution of the isolated nanoparticles after dispersion in THF on a covered holey copper grid, respectively. TEM analyses were performed at the “Service Commun de Microscopie Electronique de l’Université Paul Sabatier” (TEMSCAN-UPS) by using a JEOL JEM 1011 CX-T electron microscope operating at 100 kV with a point resolution of 4.5 Å. The approximation of the particles mean size was made through a manual analysis of enlarged micrographs by measuring a number of particles on a given grid. HRTEM observations were carried out with a JEOL JEM 2010 electron microscope working at 200 kV with a resolution point of 2.35 Å. FFT treatments have been carried out with Digital Micrograph Version 1.80.70.

Wide-angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) was performed at CEMES-CNRS. Samples were sealed in 1 mm diameter Lindemann glass capillaries. The samples were irradiated with graphite-monochromatized molybdenum K_α(0.071069) radiation and the X-ray intensity scattered measurements were performed using a dedicated two-axis diffractometer. Radial distribution functions (RDF) were obtained after Fourier Transformation of the reduced intensity functions.

Solid state NMR (MAS-NMR) with and without ¹H-¹³C cross polarization (CP) were performed at the LCC on a Bruker Avance 400WB instrument equipped with a 2.5 mm probe with the sample rotation frequency being set at 12 kHz unless otherwise indicated. Measurements were carried out in a 4 mm ZrO₂ rotor. Liquid Phase NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AMX 500 NMR and on a Bruker Avance 400 MHz spectrometers. The chemical shift calibration of the NMR spectra was done using TMS as external standard.

Gas chromatography was performed using a HP 5890 Series II Gas Chromatograph with a SGE BP1 non polar 100% dimethyl polysiloxane capillary column of 50 m x 0.32 mm x 0.25 μm. The method used for the quantification of hydrides consists of 15 min. at 40 °C and a ramp of 8 °C/min until 250 °C. The method used for styrene hydrogenation experiments consists of 3 min at 80 °C and a ramp of 8 °C/min until 210 °C.

IRFT Spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer GX2000 spectrometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹, from samples prepared as KBr pellets.

ICP analyses were performed in Antellis Toulouse and elemental analysis at the LCC.

S2. Synthesis of ruthenium nanoparticles

The ruthenium nanoparticles were prepared following a method previously described from (1,5-cyclooctadiene)(1,3,5-cyclooctatriene)ruthenium (0) complex [Ru(COD)(COT)] in the presence of variable

amounts of the ligands I^tBu or IPr under 3 bar of H_2 at room temperature, giving rise to four different colloids, as reported hereafter:

Colloid 1: $[I^tBu]/[Ru]=0.5$

$[Ru(COD)(COT)]$ (240 mg, 0.761 mmol) was introduced in a Fischer-Porter bottle and dissolved in 30 mL of freshly distilled and degassed pentane by three freeze-pump cycles. The resulting yellow solution was cooled at $-60^\circ C$ and a solution of 61 ml of pentane containing the I^tBu carbene (68 mg, 0.381 mmol) was added into the reactor. The Fischer-Porter bottle was pressurized with 3 bar of H_2 and the solution was left to reach slowly the room temperature under vigorous stirring. A black homogeneous solution was immediately formed. The reaction mixture was stirred 2h at room temperature. After this period of time, excess of H_2 was eliminated and solvent was evaporated to dryness. 50 mL of pentane were added to the resulting black residue and subsequently evaporated giving rise to a black powder that was dried overnight under vacuum.

Elemental analysis: C, 18.7%; H: 3.3%; N, 2.0%

HRTEM: NPs of 1.7 (0.2) nm

WAXS: hcp Ru nanoparticles, coherence length 2.0 nm

Colloid 2: $[IPr]/[Ru]=0.2$

$[Ru(COD)(COT)]$ (240 mg, 0.761 mmol) was introduced in a Fischer-Porter bottle and dissolved in 30 mL of freshly distilled and degassed pentane by three freeze-pump cycles. The resulting yellow solution was cooled at $-60^\circ C$ and a solution of 61 ml of pentane containing the IPr carbene (58 mg, 0.152 mmol) was added into the reactor. The Fischer-Porter bottle was pressurized with 3 bar of H_2 and the solution was left to reach slowly the room temperature under vigorous stirring. A black homogeneous solution was immediately formed. The reaction mixture was stirred 14h at room temperature. After this period of time, excess of H_2 was eliminated and solvent was evaporated to dryness. 50 mL of pentane were added to the resulting black residue and subsequently evaporated giving rise to a black powder that was dried overnight under vacuum.

Elemental analysis: C, 37.0%; H: 5.0%; N, 2.2%

HRTEM: NPs of 1.7 (0.2) nm

WAXS: hcp Ru nanoparticles, coherence length 1.7 nm

Colloid 3: $[IPr]/[Ru]=0.5$

$[Ru(COD)(COT)]$ (240 mg, 0.761 mmol) was introduced in a Fischer-Porter bottle and dissolved in 56 mL of freshly distilled and degassed pentane by three freeze-pump cycles. The resulting yellow solution was cooled at $-60^\circ C$ and a solution of 35 ml of pentane containing the IPr carbene (148 mg, 0.381 mmol) was added into the reactor. The Fischer-Porter bottle was pressurized with 3 bar of H_2 and the solution was left to reach slowly the room temperature under vigorous stirring. A black homogeneous solution was immediately formed. The reaction mixture was stirred 14h at room temperature. After this period of time, excess of H_2 was eliminated and solvent was evaporated to dryness. 50 mL of pentane were added to the resulting black residue and subsequently evaporated giving rise to a black powder that was dried overnight under vacuum.

Elemental analysis: C, 50.3%; H: 6.3%; N, 3.8%

HRTEM: NPs of 1.5 (0.2) nm

WAXS: hcp Ru nanoparticles, coherence length 1.7 nm

S3. Synthesis of labeled carbenes

Synthesis of $t\text{Bu}\cdot\text{HBF}_4\text{-}^{13}\text{C}$ ($\text{L1}^*\cdot\text{HBF}_4$). To a stirring solution of toluene (15 mL) and paraformaldehyde- ^{13}C (0.5 g, 16 mmol) at 0 °C was added dropwise *tert*-butylamine (3.5 mL, 32 mmol), under argon, over a 20 min period. The reaction mixture was stirred for a further 5 min, and then 4 mL of HCl (4 N in dioxane) was added slowly. After the reaction reached completion (no longer exothermic), the mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature, and glyoxal (40 wt %, 1.8 g, 32 mmol) was slowly added. The resulting mixture was stirred at 25 °C for 12 h. The solvent volume was concentrated almost to dryness via slow distillation by heating the reaction mixture at 105 °C for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to 50 °C, and the remaining solvent was removed under vacuum. The resulting brown solid ($t\text{Bu}\cdot\text{HCl}$) was dissolved in water (12.5 mL) and filtered, and HBF_4 (0.032 mol) was added to the solution at 0 °C to afford a white precipitate ($t\text{Bu}\cdot\text{HBF}_4$). The white solid was filtered, washed first with water (3 x 10 mL) and then with diethyl ether (2 x 10 mL) and dried under vacuum. Yield: 2.17 g (50%). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3): δ 8.83 (s, $^1J_{\text{H,C}} = 219.6$ Hz, 1H, N^{13}CHN), 7.46 (s, 2H, =CH), 1.72 (s, 18H, $t\text{Bu}$). ^{13}C { ^1H } NMR (CDCl_3): δ 131.8 (^{13}C , NCHN), 119.8 (=CH), 60.6 ($\text{C}(\text{Me})_3$), 29.5 (CH_3).

Synthesis of $t\text{Bu}\text{-}^{13}\text{C}$ (L1^*). In a drybox, tetrahydrofuran (15 mL) was added to a mixture of $t\text{Bu}\cdot\text{HBF}_4\text{-}^{13}\text{C}$ (1 g, 3.7 mmol), NaH (0.178 g, 7.4 mmol), and a catalytic amount of KO^tBu (10 mg). The resulting mixture was stirred for 12 h and the solvent was then removed under vacuum. The resulting solid was transferred to a sublimation apparatus where $t\text{Bu}$ was sublimed under static vacuum with slight heating to afford a white crystalline product. Yield: 0.6 g, (90%). ^1H NMR (C_6D_6): δ 7.56 (s, 2H, =CH), 1.89 (s, 18H, $t\text{Bu}$). ^{13}C { ^1H } NMR (C_6D_6): δ 212.8 (N^{13}CN carbene), 115.2 (=CH), 56.1 ($\underline{\text{C}}^t\text{Bu}$), 31.62 (CH_3).

Synthesis of $\text{iPr}\cdot\text{HCl}\text{-}^{13}\text{C}$ ($\text{L2}^*\cdot\text{HCl}$). 0.5 g (16 mmol) paraformaldehyde- ^{13}C (in solid form) was added to a solution of bis (2,6-diisopropylphenyl)diazabutadiene (6 g, 16 mmol)^[2] in toluene (125 mL) and heated at 100 °C till most of paraformaldehyde- ^{13}C was dissolved. It was then cooled to 40 °C and 4 mL of HCl (16 mmol, 4 M in dioxane) was injected. The reaction mixture was heated at 70 °C for 5 h during which time the color of the reaction mixture turned brown and a white precipitate appeared. The mixture was then allowed to cool to r.t. and stirred for further 36 h. The off-white precipitate was collected by filtration and washed with THF. Yield = 4.2 g (60 %). ^1H -NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 9.97 (s, $^1J_{\text{H,C}} = 222.3$ Hz, 1H, NC^{13}CHN), 8.09 (s, 2 H, =CH), 7.54 (m, 4 H, $m\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3$), 7.31 (t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 2 H, $p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3$), 2.40 (sep, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 4 H, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.24 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 12 H, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.20 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 12 H, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$). ^{13}C { ^1H } NMR (CDCl_3): δ 144.9 (C_{ortho}), 138.4 (N^{13}CHN), 132.1 (CH_{para}), 129.8 ($\text{C}_{ipso}\text{-N}_o$), 126.7 (=CH), 124.6 (CH_{meta}), 29.0 ($\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 24.6 (CH_3), 23.7 (CH_3).

Synthesis of $\text{iPr}\text{-}^{13}\text{C}$ (L2^*). THF (15 mL) was added, at r.t., to a solid mixture of $\text{iPr}\cdot\text{HCl}\text{-}^{13}\text{C}$ (1 g, 2.4 mmol) and KO^tBu (0.43 g, 3.5 mmol). The color turned brown immediately and a white precipitate was formed. The reaction mixture was stirred for 4 h, the solvent was removed in vacuo and the residue was taken up in hot toluene (~ 70 °C). The reaction mixture was then filtered and evaporation of the volatiles afforded a white solid. Yield = 780 mg (85%). ^1H -NMR (400 MHz, C_6D_6): δ 7.28 (m, 2 H, $p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3$), 7.18 (m, 4 H, $m\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3$), 6.60 (s, 2 H, =CH), 2.95 (sep, $J = 6.9$ Hz, 4 H, $\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.28 (d, $J = 6.9$ Hz, 12 H, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.18 (d, $J = 9.2$ Hz, 12 H, $\text{CH}(\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}_3)_2$). ^{13}C { ^1H }

NMR (C_6D_6): δ 220.5 ($N^{13}CN$ -carbene), 146.4 (C_{ortho}), 139.1 (C_{ipso-N}), 129.1 (CH_{para}), 123.8 (CH_{meta}), 121.7 ($=CH$), 28.9 ($\underline{C}H(CH_3)_2$), 25.0 (CH_3), 23.7 (CH_3).

S4. TEM and HREM images

Figure S1. HREM image and FFT picture obtained for Colloid 1.

Figure S2. TEM and HREM images with corresponding size histogram of Colloid **2** prepared with [IPr]/[Ru] ratio of 0.2.

Figure S3. TEM and HREM images with corresponding size histogram of Colloid **3** prepared with [IPr]/[Ru] ratio of 0.5.

Figure S4. HREM image and FFT picture obtained for Colloid **3**.

S5. Quantification of Hydrides at the surface of ruthenium nanoparticles

The general procedure for the preparation of reaction mixtures for the quantification of hydrogen atoms adsorbed onto the surface of Ru nanoparticles by CPG analyses was carried out following a previously described procedure.^[3] Each colloidal solution has been prepared in pentane. On each fresh colloidal solution, five cycles of 1 minute vacuum/1 minute bubbling of argon were performed in order to eliminate the dihydrogen solved into the solvent. Then, 5 equivalents of olefin (2-norbornene), previously filtered through alumina, were added. Samples were regularly taken from the solutions (after 4, 8 and 24 h) for CPG analyses and estimation of the olefins conversion into alkanes. To get nanoparticles-free solutions, filtration of the samples was realized through an Al₂O₃ pad.

The systems used for these measurements were: a) [I^tBu]/[Ru]=0.5; b) [IPr]/[Ru]=0.2; c) [IPr]/[Ru]=0.5.

We considered nanoparticles mean sizes and surface ruthenium atom contents as following: [I^tBu]/[Ru]=0.5 NPs (Mean size: 1.7/ 75% Surface atoms), [IPr]/[Ru]=0.2 NPs (Mean size: 1.7/ 75% Surface atoms), [IPr]/[Ru]=0.5 NPs (Mean size: 1.5/ 75% Surface atoms).

Conversion of 2-norbornene into norbornane according to initial [carbene]/[Ru] system:

	4 h	8 h	24 h
[I^tBu]/[Ru]=0.5	7.6 %	7.8 %	-
[IPr]/[Ru]=0.2	8 %	10 %	8 %
[IPr]/[Ru]=0.5	15 %	15 %	19%

Table S2. Conversion of 2-norbornene into 2-norbornane.

Quantification of hydrides according to initial [carbene]/[Ru] system:

Sample of Ru NPs	H/surface Ru atom
[I^tBu]/[Ru]=0.5	1.1
[IPr]/[Ru]=0.2	1.3
[IPr]/[Ru]=0.5	2.5

Table S3. Quantification of hydrides at the surfaces of [carbene]/[Ru] NPs.

S6. Hydrogenation of styrene

For this study, NPs were dispersed in THF inside a Fischer Porter bottle. After that, 1 mL of styrene was added in each preparation. The Fischer-Porter bottle was thus pressurized with 3 bar of H₂ and stirred at RT. Samples were taken regularly with time and analyzed by GC, after filtration through alumina.

Table

Catalytic precursor	Product ratio								
	Styrene:Ethylbenzene:Ethylcyclohexane (%)								
Time	0 h	5h	14h	33h	57h	129h	173h	217h	261h
[I ^t Bu]/[Ru]=0.5	100 : 0 : 0 0	90 : 10 : 0 0	71 : 28 : 0 0	45 : 55 : 0 0	11 : 89 : 0 1	0:94:6	0:75:25	0:65:35	0:0:100
[IPr]/[Ru]=0.5	100 : 0 : 0 0	89 : 11 : 0 0	77 : 23 : 0 0	61 : 39 : 0 0	40 : 60 : 0 0	0:98:2	0:69:30	0:0:100	-

S3.

Hydrogenation of Styrene over Ru nanoparticles. Catalytic conditions: T = 25 °C; Ratio Ru_{surface}: styrene = 1:315; [Ru_{surf}] = 4.5x10⁻³ M; gas pressure: P_{H2} = 3 bar. Determined by GC.

Graphic S1. Hydrogenation of Styrene over [I^tBu]/[Ru]=0.5 NPs (top) and [IPr]/[Ru]=0.5 NPs (bottom).

S7. Solid State reactivity experiments

For CO coordination studies, ruthenium nanoparticles were introduced in a Fischer-Porter bottle and were pressurized with 3 bar of H₂ for 14h to avoid the presence of oxygen on the surface. After this period of time, the dihydrogen gas was evacuated under vacuum for 15 min. The Fischer-Porter bottle was further pressurized with 0.5 or 0.6 bar of ¹³CO for 1 night. Then, the gas was evacuated under vacuum for 20 min. ¹³C solid state NMR was recorded after transfer of the sample into a NMR rotor.

For CO oxidation experiments, surface covered CO nanoparticles were put directly in contact with air. The evolution of the oxidation reaction was followed by ¹³C MAS-NMR with and without cross polarization and IR spectroscopy was performed as KBr pellets.

Figure S5. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR spectra of colloid **1**.

Figure S6. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR spectra of colloid **3**.

Figure S7. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR spectra of colloid **3** after exposure under ^{13}CO atmosphere (0.5 bar; 20 h; RT).

Figure S8. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR of colloid **3** exposed under ^{13}CO atmosphere and left in contact with air at RT for three days.

Figure S9. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR spectra of colloid **3***.

Figure S10. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR spectra of colloid **2***.

Figure S11. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR spectra of colloid **1***.

Figure S12. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR spectra of colloid **3*** after exposure under ^{13}CO atmosphere (0.5 bar; 19 h; RT).

Figure S13. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR spectra of colloid **2*** after exposure to a ^{13}CO atmosphere (0.6 bar; 20 h; RT).

Figure S14. ^{13}C MAS (bottom) and CP-MAS (top) NMR spectra of colloid **2*** NPs after exposure under ^{13}CO atmosphere (0.6 bar, 20 h, RT) and oxidation in contact with air (3days, RT).

S8. Space Filling and Ball & Stick representations of the coordination of L_1 and L_2 NHCs on hcp Ru NPs

The space filling model of the putative 1.8 nm hcp ruthenium nanoparticle (NP) given in Figure 6 of the main paper has been made by grafting hydrides and L_2 NHC ligands on the surface of this NP. The naked NP is a spherical piece of an hcp crystal, with Ru-Ru bond lengths set as 2.7 Å. The geometrical conformation of the L_2 NHC ligand as well as a relevant Ru-C interatomic distance (*ca.* 2.1 Å) have been determined thanks to density functional theory calculations (DFT) performed on a 18e mononuclear ruthenium complex, namely $\text{L}_2\text{Ru}(\text{PH}_3)(\text{H})_2(\text{H}_2)_2$. DFT calculations were performed with Gaussian03.^[3] Geometries have been fully optimized in gas phase without symmetry constraints, employing the B3PW91 functional^[5-11] and a polarized double-zeta quality basis set. The Stuttgart effective core potential has been used for Ru.^[12] We have shown in previous papers combining theoretical calculations of electric field gradients and experimental solid state NMR measurements^[13, 14] that Ru NPs accommodate on top, μ and μ_3 hydrides on their surface. Having in mind that the presence and stability of hydrides on the surface of different types of Ru NPs has been experimentally shown with a hydride/ surface Ru ratio greater than 1,^[15] the two main unknown parameters before building a fully capped NP are the number of L_2 NHCs co-adsorbed on the surface and the exact shape of the NP. As regards the shape, we have considered a spherical piece of an hcp crystal, although Marks decahedra could also be an interesting assumption.^[16] With the help of a software developed in our group, based on a hard sphere - or space filling - model, we have been able to coordinate 1.5 hydride per surface Ru and 8 L_2 NHC ligands which do not experience a strong steric discomfort.

Spherical piece of a Ru hcp crystal

$L_2Ru(PH_3)(H)_2(H_2)_2$ model compound

In order to shed light on the possible difference between L_1 and L_2 , we also propose in this supplementary information section to apply the same strategy for various coordination schemes on a Marks decahedron made of 192 Ru atoms. Such decahedra exhibit edges, vertices and planar Ru(0001) faces, as well as rectangular (100) facets. The ball-and-stick schemes given below show that adsorption of L_2 can easily occur on edges, whereas L_1 exhibits a more compact structure which already enters into a steric conflict with the Ru NP when adsorbed on apexes. Obviously, such steric-clash argument can also be put forward for the adsorption of L_1 on edges, whereas isopropyl functional groups in L_2 can probably adapt their orientation in order to lower the repulsive interaction with the surface. It is noteworthy that the adsorption energy of L_2 on an apex or an edge can probably be further enhanced owing to the favourable interaction of at least one phenyl group with ruthenium atoms. Finally, the adsorption on facets, although apparently more easy for L_2 with respect to L_1 , seems to be less favourable in both cases. Side (left side) and on top (right side) views are systematically given for each coordination mode.

Coordination on an apex

L₂

L₁

Coordination on an edge

L₂

L₁

Coordination on a Ru(0001) facet

L_2

L_1

S9. References

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